

Analysis and Visualisation of RO-Crate Research Data Co-design Workshop Report for the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons

The Australian Research Data Commons

09/04/2025

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15321119](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15321119)

CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS	2
THE COMMUNITY DATA LAB	3
OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS	4
THE PROJECT OPPORTUNITY AND PARTNERSHIP	4
CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP	4
NEXT STEPS	10
APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP RESPONSES	11

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarises responses from the workshop held on 18th March 2025 to co-design an upcoming ARDC infrastructure project that aims to make it easier for non-technical HASS and Indigenous researchers to work with, analyse and visualise the contents of existing RO-crates.

This project is part of the Community Data Lab, which fosters the development of tools, datasets and documentation that enable researchers to use data from galleries, libraries, museums, archives and other collections.

From 2022, the ARDC has been making a major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities. This work has been done in accordance with the 2016 NCRIS Roadmap and Department of Education commissioned studies. The projects undertaken in this area formed an emerging *HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons*.

In late 2023, the ARDC received the largest ever investment in HASS and Indigenous Research Capability. Since early 2024 we have been undergoing a process of co-design to deliver on an expanded HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons, covering existing and new areas of research infrastructure. Co-designing infrastructure investments with the research community and other stakeholders helps the ARDC to create the greatest possible impact. Development of this infrastructure follows the [HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework](#).

THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS

The ARDC is planning new investment in digital research infrastructure for HASS (Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences) and Indigenous research data communities, as part of the [HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons](#) (RDC).

The HASS and Indigenous RDC began with the identification of opportunities to accelerate the impact of HASS and Indigenous research in the [2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap](#). The Australian Government Department of Education commissioned scoping studies to identify investment-ready programs, several of which formed the foundational activities of the HASS and Indigenous RDC.

In 2023, the ARDC received its largest-ever investment in HASS research infrastructure and Indigenous research capability. This \$25 million grant, part of the Australian Government's 2023 National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) Research Infrastructure Investment Plan Funding Round, supplemented by co-investment from national partners, will further establish

long-term, national digital research infrastructure to support HASS and Indigenous research data communities in Australia.

The ARDC is currently delivering infrastructure in six focus areas, some of which builds upon foundational activities delivered during the first phase of the HASS and Indigenous RDC and some of which are new activities designed in collaboration with the research community. These are:

- Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities
- The Language Data Commons of Australia
- Social Science Research Infrastructure Network
- Australian Internet Observatory
- Australian Creative Histories and Futures
- Connections

THE COMMUNITY DATA LAB

The Community Data Lab is an ongoing activity under the Connections focus area of the HASS and Indigenous RDC. Through the Community Data Lab the ARDC seeks to improve researchers' ability to utilise the data made available from galleries, libraries, archives, museums (GLAM) and other collections. This activity provides tools, datasets and guidance that meet needs shared by researchers with different research problems from multiple disciplines. The outputs of the first phase of the Community Data Lab are now available for use by researchers.

During the delivery of this phase, the ARDC developed a set of principles for the design of sustainable HASS infrastructure, which are (in brief):

- A preference for “infrastructure at rest” over infrastructure which requires costly active support
- The separation of data from analytics
- Efficiency and flexibility of platform design
- Reusable code
- Open Source code and Open Access guidance documents

The ARDC is now in the process of developing Phase 2 of the Community Data Lab to expand this suite of data, tools and guidance materials.

OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS

The ARDC is developing this infrastructure in accordance with the HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10516606>). This process is designed to create the greatest impact for research and researchers by co-designing the infrastructure with the people who will benefit from it. Development will follow the stages of Problem Identification, Project Shaping, Project Planning, and Endorsement.

We began Problem Identification in 2024, by calling openly for registrations of interest from partners who might be able to help us to design and deliver projects for the Community Data Lab. We targeted groups at universities that provide research software engineering and data analytics support to HASS researchers, because these groups have strong experience building solutions for researchers and exposure to a range of current researcher needs. We brought potential partners together for a series of roundtable discussions. Through these discussions we identified a set of possible projects which would each serve the needs of researchers from multiple disciplines across multiple research institutions, and which could be developed in line with the principles described above.

The Project Shaping phase was implemented through the open co-design workshop described below. The workshop was advertised through ARDC newsletters, social media channels and other networks. We sought to involve experts in research practice, disciplinary needs and infrastructure provision to better understand the current challenges faced by stakeholders and the outcomes that they hope to see, and to shape potential solutions that could be provided by the new infrastructure.

Project Planning and Endorsement phases will follow - further information is provided in the “Next Steps” section below.

THE PROJECT OPPORTUNITY AND PARTNERSHIP

The proposed project aims to make it easier for non-technical HASS and Indigenous researchers to work with, analyse and visualise the contents of existing RO-crates. This project is being developed in partnership with Melbourne Data Analytics Platform (MDAP), The University of Melbourne.

CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP

The co-design workshop was held virtually on 18 March 2025. The workshop was open to all and was attended by 28 participants from 12 organisations. Organisations represented included 6 Australian universities and 1 international university, as well as government organisations, research infrastructure providers, research institutions and industry.

The workshop aimed to refine our understanding of the challenge, validate the problem statement and its impact, confirm the user base for the proposed solution, and gather feedback on the proposed solution's features. A/Prof Nic Geard and Dr Daniel Russo-Batterham (Melbourne Data Analytics Platform, The University of Melbourne) presented on the challenge, which was summarised with the following problem statement:

“RO-Crates are a valuable way to preserve important collections in the humanities, arts, and social sciences (HASS) and galleries, libraries, archives, and museums (GLAM) sectors, along with their metadata and linkage information. However, there are not many tools available for using RO-Crates in research, such as for analysing and visualising the collections stored in them. Current tools help create RO-Crates as archival objects, but more work is needed to make these objects useful for research”

Participants completed a series of discussion activities in breakout groups, and recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Some key themes from the responses are highlighted below - full responses can be found in Appendix 1.

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

Have we described the problem correctly?

- Validity of the problem statement
 - I have dozens of legacy projects converted to ro-crate and a few that are still active however I do not use the ro-crate form of the data due to a lack of tools. I think the problem statement is correct
 - I think the statement of the problem is good, in particular the emphasis on user accessibility - usable tools and supporting them. So to expand - it will be important to people currently using RO Crate but also researchers in the research grant application phase making critical decisions about how to make a database
- Examples of RO-Crate use cases
 - Survey of plastics in collections of 6 museums
 - Possible use for medical data
- Existing tools and solutions
 - Could leverage existing Linked Data tools (e.g. triple-stores, visualisation tools, etc). We may not need to reinvent wheels
 - RO-crate is used in other research domains (e.g. genomics). We need to work in concert with the existing RO-crate organisation to ensure that any development is widely applicable
- User needs and accessibility

- Researchers (other than corpus linguist and research archivists) generally require an array of visualisation metaphors to be research productive
- Need to make clear to researchers that files added to RO-Create need to be in formats suitable for digital preservation if they see this as a long-term archive

Who is this problem important to?

- Researchers and data owners
 - Lots of RO-crate curious researchers
 - Researchers with lots of project web site outputs
 - Heurist and OHRM data creators/owners
- Research support personnel and funders
 - RSE (research software/support engineers) and RDM (data management) engineers who need to provide tools to researchers to work with
 - Research support specialists helping to plan or execute projects
 - Funders seeking increased return on their investments, through production of more accessible sustainable data.
- Individuals who would benefit from using RO-Crates
 - People looking to preserve complex linked data and files
 - Anyone who wants to use RO-Crates to publish structured data
- Archivists and repository managers
- Other comments
 - A pilot undertaken with developing a visualisation UX on top of RO-Crate for the OMAA project was well received by cultural historians
 - Potential for the RO-Crates exported from the curated collections project might constitute a coherent schema distinct from the linguistic schema developed in LDACA
 - Researchers who create Data Management Plans have already created some of the metadata that could be used later in a Crate

Would addressing this problem be valuable (what would be enabled if we solved this problem?)

- Improved data interoperability and flexibility
 - Increase interoperability with system data export and import
 - Reduction in time lost due to changing platforms / formats - ability to easily migrate, transferability.
- Sustainability and long-term preservation
 - Huge improvement in sustainability of data
 - Data will remain usable into the future
- Improved data discovery and access
 - Improves discoverability of archives

- Improved serendipitous discovery of materials through contextual links between resources
- Research collaboration and reproducibility
 - It can enable people doing meta-analyses of existing crates that were not necessarily collected by them
 - More opportunities to improve peer review of digital outputs, establishing expectations to use standards like RO Crate for research data management.
- Workflow improvement
 - Reduce redundancy in data storage
 - Structured data would be easily analysed and processed
- Data quality and provenance
 - RO-Crates have inbuilt provenance features so you can point to tools and code used to create things
 - Recording, mapping data provenance and transformations (even audit trails)

Activity 2: If you have used RO-Crates before to store research data, what do you find most challenging about using RO-crates for research data? If you have not used RO-Crates to store research data, what is the primary reason? Give specific real world examples.

- Complexity and learning curve
 - Learning how to use them and educating others how to use them
 - Introducing linked data to researchers is challenging: IRIs, JSON-LD, graphs are complex!
 - RO-Crate as a spec is aimed at developers and metadata people
 - Time and effort of initial setup, either at start, or converting existing data to RO-crate
- Terminology
 - In Humanities you deal with people and not objects. The terminology of RO-Crates is turning a lot of researchers off
- Tools and infrastructure issues
 - Need for automated approaches to scale up from manual construction of small data sets
 - Where one might host RO-Crates seems unresolved
 - Querying/searching crates is difficult. SPARQL seems to be a good solution but extremely complex
 - A lot of the existing tooling is quite high-level (easy to use but lacking flexibility) or quite low level (the RO-Crate Python package, for instance, which allows flexible access to data and contextual entities but would take a lot of code to find meaningful subsets of entities and relationships let alone meaningfully analyse and visualise them)
- Standards and metadata issues

- Validating RO-Crates seems subjective
- There's a lack of schemas in HASS - we should look at starting some small-S standards work for describing History etc
- How easy is it to maintain/update metadata in a crate once established?
- Relevance
 - Hadn't used them before because I wasn't familiar with them
 - To invest in ro-crate one needs to see a relevance to research outputs
 - It is not the major export and import format used in common systems yet
- Other comments
 - Making sure that we don't make new schemas when there are existing ones that can be applied
 - An interesting alternative to SPARQL might be GraphQL, since it maps quite neatly to the way Crates are naturally structured.

Activity 3: Do you have research data that you would like to or that is already stored in RO-crates? How would you like to visualise this data to make it more accessible for research?

- Interoperability and platform integration
 - Archiving is great, but portability, and the ability to migrate from one platform to another (eg; Omeka to Wordpress or vice versa) is important too
 - Export RO-Crate from Omeka S
 - Exporting RO-Crate from TLCMap
- Visualisation needs and preferences
 - Could you annotate/layer context on top of the graph?
 - Visualisation of both the whole bucket - corpus - but also crucially of smaller elements within the corpus. So macro vs micro analysis and visualisation - both are important!
 - Visualisation is a way of understanding the logic by which an RO-Crate is constructed especially if you did not assemble the data or create
- Challenges with current tools and complex data
 - Existing tools don't explain what all the properties mean and are overwhelming
 - Traditional graph query languages have been tried but are too complex for generalised HASS and Indigenous researchers
 - Challenges associated with visualisation of very large data sets. how do you prune, abstract or otherwise reduce the scale of data sets
- Examples of desired data to be stored
 - <https://opentelemetry.io/>
 - Encyclopedia of Australian Science and Innovation

- Linguistic recordings and interviews
- Timeline and geo-spatial mapping
- Other comments
 - OMMA project exposed, generous archives, spreadsheets, node graphs and mapping as productive visualisation metaphors
 - Investment in Crate-O would be good as others have noted that it is not that mature. Crate-O roadmap included aspirations to become the sort of thing that could be used to edit large-scale HASS collections

Activity 4: Would you like to analyse and link together data across different RO-Crates? If so, give an example of how you would use this capability, for example, to create network graphs. If not, what would be a more valuable capability for your research?

- Data linkage and integration
 - In principle, RO-Crates allow adding identifiers to entities for data linkage: in practice, this would involve a lot of work
 - RO-crate is one format of Linked Data. We need to be careful not to conflate Linked Data as a whole with RO-crate
 - Challenge of doing this is that RO-Crates within a single system can be easily searched across and analysed, but if they are in separate systems then providing this analysis becomes trickier as the data needs to be accessible from the one location to analyse
- Tools and technology for data analysis
 - Need tools to help crosswalking between schemas
 - Can AI tools, LLM instrument existing collections to build connections between items?
 - Use semantic search to build connections?
- Reusing and reorganising data
 - This would be valuable if it would allow you to analyse data in RO-Crates created by different researchers over time
 - Ideally visualisation and analysis components could be reused by other open-source platforms and tools
 - Recreate RO-Crate repo that can be searched across; create project or community based RO-Crates from open RO-Crate, search/link them
- Data interoperability
 - Don't underestimate the power of basic interop metadata -- a simple index like Zenodo can ingest basic crates and make them discoverable with full-text search

NEXT STEPS

The ARDC has worked with the potential project team to develop a draft project plan, released for public feedback alongside the publication of this report. Feedback submissions will close end of day Friday 23 May. To submit feedback on project plans please use the form on the ARDC website. All feedback will be collated and responded to in a published report, alongside an updated project plan taking into account this feedback wherever possible. Work on this project is planned to commence in July 2025.

The development of the resulting infrastructure will involve ongoing public testing and consultation - please make sure you are signed up to the HASS and I newsletter so that you receive notifications about upcoming opportunities to be involved.

If you have any other comments or questions about this process please contact us at hassi.codesign@ardc.edu.au with the subject line 'RO-Crates'.

APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP RESPONSES

Full text of workshop responses

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Have we described the problem correctly?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Speaking as a member of the RO-Crate team: Yep +2 ● Yes, most conference talks and software packages I've seen are concerned with creating crates and not analysing them ● I have dozens of legacy projects converted to ro-crate and a few that are still active however I do not use the ro-crate form of the data due to a lack of tools. I think the problem statement is correct. ● Example: survey of plastics in collections of 6 museums ● Items linked in a relational database ● 10,000 digital objects not easily publicly available ● Preserved but links hard to see/understand ● Possible use for Medical data? ● Could leverage existing Linked Data tools (e.g. triple-stores, visualisation tools, etc.) - we may not need to reinvent wheels ● Redbox > RDBMS > RO-crates for publishing ● researchers (other than corpus linguist and research archivists) generally require an array of visualisation metaphors to be research productive +1 ● As a current non RO-Crate user, I needed to do prior reading before understanding the problem. ● RO-crate is used in other research domains (e.g. genomics). We need to work in concert with the existing RO-crate organisation to ensure that any development is widely applicable. +3 ● Need to make clear to researchers that files added to RO-Create need to be in formats suitable for digital preservation if they see this as a long-term archive ● May also need to consider creation. Not always good tools for researchers to be able to crete ROC (Omeka S export one part of solution, but not necessarily for all researchers/data) ● "I think the statement of the problem is good, in particular the emphasis on user accessibility - usable tools and supporting them. So to expand - it will be important to people currently using RO Crate but ALSO to researchers in the research grant application phase making critical decisions about how to make a database - what kind, how supported and so on

QUESTION	RESPONSES
----------	-----------

<p>Who is the problem important to?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● RSE (research software/support engineers) and RDM (data management) engineers who need to provide tools to researchers to work with ● Heurist and OHRM data creators/owners ● Researchers with Lots of project web site outputs ● (Researchers with Lots of project web site outputs) Agreed ● helps separate the data from publishing it (i.e. not encapsulated in a cheap website builder) ● CDL phase 2 as a whole needs to communicate about the importance and value of RO-Crates ● Researchers building collections in software platforms like Omeka S, who want a format which will outlive the platform ● Researchers planning projects ● Researchers collaborating across organisations, requiring standardised methods to share data ● Lots of RO-crate curious researchers ● Lots of technical people with passing acquaintance ● pilot undertaken with developing a visualisation UX on top of RO-Crate for the OMAA project was well received by cultural historians ● Funders seeking increased ROI on their investments, through production of more accessible sustainable data. ● Archivists and those interested in the longer-term sustainability of data. ● (Archivists and those interested in the longer-term sustainability of data.) Important to stitch this together with the Omeka S project ● researchers and people working with the data ● Anyone who wants to use RO-Crates to publish structured data ● Are RO-crates suitable for archiving medical data / records ? ● people who would benefit from RO-Crates but don't know they exist! ● Potential for the RO-Crates exported from the curated collections project might constitute a coherent schema distinct form the linguistic schema developed in LDACA ● repository managers who would benefit from a bigger toolset ● researchers who create Data Management Plans have already created some of the metadata that could be used later in a Crate ● People looking to preserve complex linked data and files ● Research support specialists helping to plan or execute projects ● People with very large collections or Crates that are difficult to work with ● People looking to leverage RO-Crate workflows from other domains ● People working with research platforms that support import or export of Crates ● Historians: wanting to zoom in to a network on a micro-level
---	---

QUESTION	RESPONSES
----------	-----------

<p>Would addressing this problem be valuable? (what would be enabled if we solved this problem?)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● RO-Crates have a narrow waist that enables lots of input sources and lots of output possibilities to interact. (also idea of an interface) ● Reduce redundancy in data storage ● More opportunities to improve peer review of digital outputs, establishing expectations to use standards like RO Crate for research data management. ● Huge improvement in sustainability of DATA (previous conversations often look at project or service sustainability) ● Improvements in reproducibility ● It can enable people doing meta analyses of existing crates that were not necessarily collected by them ● RO-Crates have inbuilt provenance features so you can point to tools and code used to create things ● Improved serendipitous discovery of materials through contextual links between resources and being able to extend these - particularly if can be displayed in such a way that doesn't require researchers to be able to create a SPARQL or other complex query to access the data ● Reduction in time lost due to changing platforms / formats - ability to easily migrate. Transferability. ● Recording, mapping data provenance and transformations (even audit trails) ● improves discoverability of archives ● enable easier data processing and data workflow ● Could RO-crates record data quality metadata, to help automate DQ ? ● Better viability of RO-Crate as an end-to-end metadata format ● Some large collections exist >10k digital items - archived but not easily accessible ● Structured data would be easily analyzed and processed ● increase interoperability with system data export and import +1 ● Data will remain usable into the future
--	--

Activity 2

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>If you have used RO-Crates before to store research data, what do you find most challenging about using RO-crates for research data? If you have not used RO-Crates to store research data, what is the primary reason? Give specific real world examples</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Archivist - tools Crato and Describo are not particularly mature +1 ● Used them to describe data collections published on an institutional data portal ● Keen to explore them but haven't found the time. ● in Humanities you deal with people and not objects. The terminology of RO-Crates is turning a lot of researchers off. ● How easy is it to maintain/update metadata in a crate once established? ● Where one might host RO-Crates seems unresolved ● Hadn't used them before because I wasn't familiar with them ● lots of people (researchers?) have data but don't really understand metadata or the need for it ● Initial set up, learning curve, ensuring all collaborators are on board, trained and across the functionality. Governance questions.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● all of your vocabs have to have IRIs(?) ● profiles is really complex, not in the published spec ● describing data that isn't in the schema.org vocab ● time and effort of initial setup, either at start, or converting existing data to RO-crate ● related to these green boxes - there's a lack of schemas in HASS we should look at starting some small-S standards work for describing History etc +1 ● adapting existing metadata standards is difficult without identifiers... ● Need for automated approaches to scale up from manual construction of small data sets. +1 ● to invest in ro-crate one needs to see a relevance to research outputs ● learning how to use them and educating others how to use them +2 ● Generating RO-Crate best generated automatically from mature platforms (e.g Omeka S) ● Remember RO-Crate as a spec is aimed at developers and metadata ppl so they can build tools ● not many systems support it yet? ● could be useful as a format for sharing data associated with publications ● It is not the major export and import format used in common systems yet ● Validating RO-Crates seems subjective... +2 ● Querying/searching crates is difficult. SPARQL seems to be a good solution but extremely complex +1 ● Introducing linked data to researchers is challenging: IRIs, JSON-LD, graphs are complex! +1 ● Making sure that we don't make new schemas when there are existing ones that can be applied ● There are questions around how to effectively search large Crates, without the need to spin up production-grade search engine like ElasticSearch ● A lot of the existing tooling is quite high-level (easy to use but lacking flexibility) or quite low level (the RO-Crate Python package, for instance, which allows flexible access to data and contextual entities but would take a lot of code to find meaningful subsets of entities and relationships let along meaningfully analyse and visualise them). ● An interesting alternative to SPARQL might be GraphQL, since it maps quite neatly to the way Crates are naturally structured.
--	--

Activity 3

QUESTION	RESPONSES
Do you have research data that you would like to or that is already stored in RO-crates? How would	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Archiving is great, but portability, and the ability to migrate from one platform to another (eg; Omeka to Wordpress or vice versa) is important too. +1 ● I'm interested in storing https://opentelemetry.io/ data? A

<p>you like to visualise this data to make it more accessible for research?</p>	<p>formative idea...,https://opentelemetry.io/, https://opentelemetry.io/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Archive RO-Crates from Omeka ● OMMA project exposed, generous archives, spreadsheets, node graphs and mapping as productive visualisation metaphors.+1 ● Visualising the graph as a graph ● Current tools overwhelming (clouds of links) ● exporting RO-Crate from TLCMap ● Investment in Crate-O would be good as others have noted that it is not that mature. Crate-O roadmap included aspirations to become the sort of thing that could be used to edit large-scale HASS collections (like Heurist, OHRM and Omeka) Getting a roadmap for tools for the CDL would be good - maybe via the ANU project ● What kinds of visualisation? ● linguistic recordings and interviews. Dashboard to show data composition would be nice. ● Want to know how or why entities are connected? ● Could you annotate/layer context on top of the graph? +1 ● visualisation - what is the purpose: exploration, analysis, communication, etc. Informs what the best choices are for visualisation, interactivity, etc ● Existing tools don't explain what all the properties mean +1 ● Complex ro-crates have complex properties that are not easy to understand ● E.g. provenance, this created this - not laid out sequentially or in timeline ● Yes, Encyclopedia of Australian Science and Innovation. Network graph tools that produce filtered SVG files with links to URIs for metadata about the entities or nodes ● (Yes, Encyclopedia of Australian Science and Innovation. Network graph tools that produce filtered SVG files with links to URIs for metadata about the entities or nodes) Visualisation of both the whole bucket - corpus - but also crucially of smaller elements within the corpus. So macro vs micro analysis and visualisation - both are important! ● Export ro-crate from Omeka S +1 ● if location data in the metadata, s geographic map of the crate would be useful ● timeline and geo-spatial mapping ● Visualisation is a way of understanding the logic by which an RO-Crate is constructed especially if you did not assemble the data or create ● traditional graph query languages have been tried but are too complex for generalised HASS&I researchers ● challenges associated with visualisation of very large data sets. how do you prune, abstract or otherwise reduce the scale of data sets ● A way to easily visualise the structure of an unfamiliar Crate which isn't just a network diagram (which for large crates will just be a hairball) ● Inherited data is one important use case - databases that might be decades old and need replatforming. And if the current RO-C
---	---

	<p>technology allows visualisations for example that would not have been possible in the original format that would be great</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Helping to find the right subset of data to visualise will be a key challenge. Graph query languages like Cypher and so on are not accessible to most HASS researchers. ● Grouping data files visually based on relevant subsets of metadata. You can imagine a dataset with lots of images, for instance, wanting to catalog or visualise these in a very nuanced way that helps with specific research questions. ● Mapping temporal dimensions as well relationships ● Geospatial visualisations of data and metadata that incorporate temporal dimensions too (a timeline)
--	--

Activity 4

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Would you like to analyse and link together data across different RO-Crates? If so, give an example of how you would use this capability, for example, to create network graphs. If not, what would be a more valuable capability for your research?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Don't underestimate the power of basic interop metadata -- a simple index like Zenodo can ingest basic crates and make them discoverable with full-text search ● Linked data sounds really promising, but linking vs gathering relies on trusting the link will always work/the data will always be there ● Need tools to help crosswalking between schemas ● In principle, RO-Crates allow adding identifiers to entities for data linkage: in practice, this would involve a lot of work +1 ● This scenario is not applicable for us ● recreate rocrate repo that can be searched across; create project or community based rocrates from open rocrate, search/link them ● RO-crate is one format of Linked Data. We need to be careful not to conflate Linked Data as a whole with RO-crate. +1 ● linking out to reliable sources (eg wikidata) to augment data and connections ● Yes ● I think linking across Crates would be particularly relevant to people looking to "reuse" Creates created by others. ● Challenge of doing this is that RO-Crates within a single system can be easily searched across and analysed, but if they are in separate systems then providing this analysis becomes trickier as the data needs to be accessible from the one location to analyse ● Ideally visualisation and analysis components could be reused by other open-source platforms and tools ● Tools for deriving relationships implicitly from the data (using LLMS and the like?), since often there aren't the resources available in HASS projects for people to make explicit links ● This would be valuable if it would allow you to analyse data in RO-Crates created by different researchers over time. +1

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● analyse current 'collections' and form new links based on a new relationship● break down the structure and rebuild it● requires expert help to reprocess ro-crate data and create new relationships● Particularly the case when reusing previously collected data, or data collected by different people / organisations● using semantic search to build connections?● e.g. build relationships between 'patterns' in music● Can AI tools, llms instrument existing collections to build connections between items?● speeds up the process, substitutes for human judgement in making connections● How to do something to make it more likely that linking data will be possible in the future● Natural language operations with data.
--	---